

Photochemistry of Co(III)-penta-ammine Oxalate and Co(III)-tetra-ammine *bis*-Oxalate Complexes

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Photochemistry of Co(III)-penta-ammine oxalate and Co(III)-tetra-ammine-*bis* oxalate complexes has been studied in aqueous solution ($pH = 4.63 - 2.7$) using different wavelengths of irradiation under both aerobic and anaerobic media. Quantum yields of redox and aquated products have been determined. For penta-ammine oxalate complex the redox yield increases in the order $490 < 420 < 313 < 366 < 254$ and for tetra-ammine *bis*-oxalate complex the order being $420 \approx 366 < 313 < 254$. The redox and aquation yields decrease slightly with decrease in pH . Redox yield in anaerobic medium is higher (almost double) than that in aerobic medium, due to scavenging of $C_2O_4^{2-}$ radical by oxygen (evidenced by formation of H_2O_2) in the latter case. In general the simple radical pair model is not sufficient to explain the photochemical behaviour of the complexes; the distribution of product yields depends on the spectroscopic state of excited species.

THE photochemistry of Co(III) coordination compounds has been extensively studied^{1,2} and the compounds have intricate photochemical behaviour. Various features of the photochemistry of these compounds suggest that a simple generalization can not be applied to this class of compounds. They exhibit two types of photoreactions, the photoredox and photosubstitution reactions. Irradiation in the ligand field bands generally produce substitution products while irradiation in CTM band results in redox decomposition along with photosubstitution.

The photochemistry of $[Co(NH_3)_5HC_2O_4]^{2+}$ and $[Co(NH_3)_4C_2O_4]^+$ have been previously studied by Felipescu *et al*³ and Endicott *et al*⁴. They reported only the quantum yield of formation of reduced metal ion and proposed a mechanism. No estimation, nor detection, of other possible photoproducts was made. In the present study photolysis of the complexes have been investigated using 490, 420, 366, 313 and 254 nm radiations. Quantum yields of Co^{2+} , ammonia and oxalate have been determined. Effects of pH , anaerobicity and initial concentration of the complex on quantum yields have been studied with an aim to understand the detailed stoichiometry of the photoreaction.

Experimental

Materials: The complexes $[Co(NH_3)_5HC_2O_4]^{2+}$ and $[Co(NH_3)_4C_2O_4]^+$ prepared according to literature procedures⁵⁻⁷, were twice recrystallized and purity of the complexes determined by estimating Co^{2+} and ammonia after decomposition. Double distilled water and analytical grade reagents were used in all the experiments.

Photolysis arrangements:

Photolysis of the complexes with light of different wavelengths were performed in a long necked

rectangular quartz cell (path length 1 cm; volume 4 ml). The cell was held in an aluminium block (10 cm \times 10 cm \times 10 cm) with a rectangular slot (2.2 cm \times 1.1 cm \times 6 cm) at the front. The system was kept at a constant temperature of $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ by circulating water from thermostatic bath through the channels drilled in the aluminium block. 490 and 420 nm light were isolated from a 150 watt tungsten filament lamp using proper glass filters. 366 and 313 nm light were obtained from a medium pressure mercury vapour lamp (H_g lamp) and the 254 nm radiation from a low pressure mercury vapour lamp (M/s. Thermal Syndicate, model T/M5/594, 100 watt). The lamps were mounted vertically on an optical bench. The light was collimated by two quartz convex lenses mounted on the same bench and then passed through the appropriate filters (to isolate the desired wavelength) before falling on the reaction cell. For isolating 366 nm radiation, a Chance's O-O-glass and copper sulfate solution (250 g/litre in 0.01N H_2SO_4) of 1 cm path length filters were used. To isolate 313 nm radiation potassium chromate (0.27 g/litre in 0.02 N Na_2CO_3) solution of 1 cm path length was used.

Solutions to be photolyzed were prepared (10^{-4} and $10^{-5} M/l$) from the solid immediately before use and placed in the irradiation compartment 30 min before the start of irradiation to attain the equilibrium temperature of 35° . Solutions of pH 4.63, 3.72 and 3.42 were prepared by using acetate buffer and those of pH 1.2 and 2.4 were prepared in $6.31 \times 10^{-2} N HClO_4$ and $3.98 \times 10^{-3} N HClO_4$, respectively. The pH of the solutions were measured by Elico digital pH meter, Model LI-120.

For deoxygenation, nitrogen gas from the cylinder (Indian Oxygen Ltd.) was first bubbled through Jones reductor containing Zn-amalgam in vanadous sulphate solution to free it of any trace of oxygen if present. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through a presaturator before bubbling it in the experimental

solution in the cell. The gas was bubbled through the experimental solution for ~1 hr by means of a hypodermic needle passing through a tightly fitting rubber latex cap placed on the neck of the cell. The needle was raised above the surface of the solution and passing of gas was continued at a very slow rate during photolysis. Photolysis was also performed in presence of oxygen in an identical manner.

Cobalt(II) produced on photolysis was determined using a modification of Kitson's method⁶ which involves the measurement of the absorption at 625 nm of the Co(II) thiocyanate complex formed in the water-acetone mixture. ($\epsilon_{625} = 2.00 \times 10^3$ l.M⁻¹cm⁻¹). A colorimetric method using Nessler's reagent was adopted to estimate the released ammonia. Ammonia in alkaline medium produced an orange red colouration with potassium mercuric iodide, which has an absorption maxima at the wavelength range 420-425 nm ($\epsilon_{420} = 2.99 \times 10^3$ l.M⁻¹cm⁻¹). The interfering free Co²⁺ ion was complexed with EDTA before adding the Nessler reagent for developing colour from ammonia. A calibration curve was drawn with standard ammonium chloride solution containing Co(II) ion. The photoreleased oxalate ion was estimated by titrating with a standard solution of potassium permanganate. H₂O₂ produced on aerobic irradiation was estimated by the triiodide method of Allen *et al.*⁶ Optical density of the solution was measured at 350 nm (absorption maxima of I₃⁻) against a blank solution. Optical densities were measured with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

Ferri-oxalate actinometry was performed in the reaction cell before and after each experiment to determine the light output.

Results and Discussion

The electronic absorption spectra of tri-positive cobalt complexes (hexacoordinate, low spin) have in general three principal regions of absorption. The intense bands in the vicinity of 230-300 nm are assigned as spin-allowed ligand to metal charge-transfer transition (CTTM). The other two are ligand-field (d-d) bands, one of which is located in the region 345-415 nm (L₂ band) and the other around 475-625 nm (L₁ band), the actual position depending on the strength of the ligand field. The absorption spectra of Co(III)-penta-ammine oxalate and Co(III)-tetra-ammine *bis*-oxalate in aqueous solution show that the ligand field L₁ band $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ lies around 505-510 nm for both the complexes. With tetra-ammine complex, the ligand field L₂ band, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$, appearing at 358 nm is separated from the lowest CTTM band (strong absorption below 310 nm). With penta-ammine complex, no isolated L₂ band is observed probably due to red shifting of the lowest CTTM band. A strong absorption at 390 nm to lower uv is a result of superimposition of the L₂ and CTTM bands. The spectra of tetra-ammine *bis*-oxalato complex is independent of pH in the region of pH 6 to 2M HClO₄, but that of penta-ammine complex showed

variation with pH, and a new band appeared in the 290 nm region as the pH was raised, indicative of the acid dissociation reaction⁴ (for which $pK_a = 2.2$), $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{H})]^{2+} \rightleftharpoons [\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]^{+} + \text{H}^{+}$. Similar spectral dependence on pH in that region is also observed for $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^{-} \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-} + \text{H}^{+}$ (though the extinction is much lower), suggesting that possibly the 290 nm band is due to intraligand transition.

The progressive decrease in the characteristic absorption peaks of Co(III) complex after irradiation with light in the above wavelengths and the absence of significant changes in the absorption spectra in the dark period indicated that dark reactions (thermal) were negligible.

Results, summarized in Table 1, show that photoredox yields, $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$, at various wave-lengths for tetra-ammine *bis*-oxalato complex increase in the order of 420 \approx 366 < 313 < 254 nm and this supports the radical pair model as proposed by Adamson. For penta-ammine oxalato complex, however, $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ shows complex wavelength dependence, (Fig. 1), the order being 490 < 420 < 313 < 366 < 254 nm. Similar complex wavelength dependence of redox has also been reported with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NCS}]^{2+}$. In this respect, it is worth

Fig. 1. Wavelength dependence of redox quantum yields for Co(III)-tetra-ammine *bis*-oxalato and Co(III)-penta-ammine oxalato complexes.

mentioning that both oxalate and thiocyanate ligand have intraligand absorption bands (due to transition between molecular orbitals which are localised on the ligand system) in the uv region. In the present work, photolysis of the complexes were done in the pH range 3.4 to 4.6, where the penta-ammine oxalato complex exists in the form $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]^{+}$ and this form has additional absorption band around 290 nm compared to the acid form $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{H})]^{2+}$, as reported earlier⁴. This band at 290 nm has been assigned to be due to intraligand transition. So the absorption at 313 nm of the penta-ammine complex at pH 3.4

TABLE 1—QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co(II), NH₃, C₂O₄²⁻ FOR Co(II)-TETRA-AMMINE Bis-OXALATO AND Co(III)-PENTA-AMMINE OXALATO COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT pH AND WAVELENGTHS IN AEROBIC MEDIA ; TEMP. 35°

Complex	Irradiation wavelength nm	Conc. of complex moles/liter	pH	φ _{Co³⁺}	φ _{NH₃}	φ _{C₂O₄²⁻}	φ _{AA} ^a	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ HC ₂ O ₄] ²⁺	490	4.03 × 10 ⁻³	4.63	0.005	0.055	0.051	0.031	
			3.72	0.005	0.052	0.050	0.031	
			2.72	0.005	0.049	0.045	0.021	
	420	7.50 × 10 ⁻³	4.63	0.171	1.19	0.472	0.34	
			3.72	0.139	0.96	0.470	0.27	
			2.72	0.124	0.80	0.443	0.18	
	366	2.0 × 10 ⁻³	4.63	0.290	2.02	0.220	0.57	
			3.72	0.262	1.73	0.201	0.43	
			3.42	0.251	1.50	0.190	0.24	
		5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.63	0.168	0.90	0.085	0.10	
			3.72	0.145	0.78	0.078	0.06	
			3.42	0.135	0.72	0.073	0.05	
		254	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.63	0.424	3.91	0.366	1.79
				3.72	0.393	3.55	0.342	1.58
				3.42	0.374	3.28	0.335	1.41
	2.40			0.365	2.86	0.394	1.04	
	1.20			0.316	2.46	0.369	0.88	
	420	6.6 × 10 ⁻³	4.63	0.203	2.38	0.660	1.57	
3.72			0.196	2.01	0.513	1.23		
2.72			0.174	1.65	0.430	0.95		
366	2.0 × 10 ⁻³	4.63	0.197	1.43	0.143	0.64		
		3.72	0.176	1.31	0.137	0.61		
		3.42	0.168	1.20	0.130	0.53		
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ C ₂ O ₄] ⁺	313	5.0 × 10 ⁻³	4.63	0.295	1.34	0.151	0.16	
			3.72	0.278	1.25	0.141	0.14	
			3.42	0.267	1.22	0.136	0.15	
	254	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.63	0.435	3.03	0.3·3	0.16	
			3.72	0.395	2.54	0.352	0.96	
			3.42	0.380	2.29	0.344	0.77	
			2.40*	0.401	2.24	0.375	0.64	
			1.20*	0.450	2.62	0.390	0.82	

* O₂ bubbled during irradiation.

Quantum yield for the formation of H₂O₂ in aerobic condition for tetra-ammine complex at 254 nm, pH 3.72, Temp. 35° was φ_{H₂O₂} = 0.037.

^a φ_{AA} - Ammonia aquated products for penta and tetra-ammine complexes.

to 4.6 is, at least partly, due to intraligand transition and the lower quantum yield of redox process at this wavelength is due to the reason that communication between intraligand band and CTTM band is not efficient.

In anaerobic condition, quantum yields of the aquated products were calculated by subtracting the yields of oxalate and ammonia which would be produced if only redox process took place, from the total yield of oxalate and ammonia. For penta-ammine complex,

$$\phi_{[Co(NH_3)_5(H_2O)]^{2+}} = \phi_{C_2O_4^{2-}(T)} - \frac{1}{2}\phi_{Co^{2+}}$$

$$\phi_{[Co(NH_3)_4C_2O_4(H_2O)]^+} = \phi_{NH_3(T)} - 5\phi_{Co^{2+}}$$

For tetra-ammine complex,

$$\phi_{[Co(NH_3)_4(H_2O)_2]^{2+}} = \phi_{C_2O_4^{2-}(T)} - \frac{1}{2}\phi_{Co^{2+}}$$

$$\phi_{[Co(NH_3)_3C_2O_4(H_2O)]^+} = \phi_{NH_3(T)} - 4\phi_{Co^{2+}}$$

In aerobic condition, oxalate-aquated product was calculated from the following relation

$$\phi_{[Co(NH_3)_5(H_2O)_2]^{2+}} = \phi_{C_2O_4^{2-}} - [\phi_{Co^{2+}} - \frac{1}{2}\phi_{C_2O_4^{2-}}(anaerobic)]$$

$$\phi_{[Co(NH_3)_4(H_2O)_2]^{2+}} = \phi_{C_2O_4^{2-}} - [\phi_{Co^{2+}} - \frac{1}{2}\phi_{C_2O_4^{2-}}(anaerobic)]$$

The photo-redox and photoaquation quantum yields (Table 1) are slightly pH dependent and the yields increase with decrease in pH. As suggested by Filipescu *et al*⁵ the decrease in redox yield with increase in acidity may be due to scavenging of C₂O₄^{·-} radical by hydrogen ion. Redox quantum yield values for 254 nm radiation of the complexes in perchloric acid media (pH 1.2 and 2.4) show good agreement with those reported earlier by Endicott *et al*⁴.

Though Filipescu *et al*⁵ reported earlier that [Co(NH₃)₅C₂O₄]⁺ is less photo-sensitive than the tetra-ammine complex, the present investigation shows that with 254 nm irradiation both give almost the same photo-redox yield. With 366 nm radiation,

TABLE 2—QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co(II), NH₃, C₂O₄²⁻ FOR Co(III)-TETRA-AMMINE *Bis*-OXALATO AND Co(III)-PENTA-AMMINE OXALATO COMPLEXES AT pH 3.72 AT DIFFERENT WAVELENGTHS IN ANAEROBIC MEDIA, TEMP. 35°

Complex	Irradiation wavelength nm	Conc. of complex moles/liter	$\phi_{Co^{2+}}$	ϕ_{NH_3}	$\phi_{C_2O_4^{2-}}$	ϕ_{AA} (Calcd)
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ HC ₂ O ₄] ⁺	366	1.5 × 10 ⁻³	0.455	3.38	0.400	1.10
		2.0 × 10 ⁻³	0.470	3.43	0.403	1.08
		2.5 × 10 ⁻³	0.482	3.51	0.411	1.10
	313	4.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.162	0.88	0.142	0.070
		4.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.187	1.01	0.149	0.075
		5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.1999	1.08	0.152	0.085
	254	0.75 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.581	4.13	0.724	1.23
		1.00 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.599	4.34	0.766	1.35
		1.25 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.627	4.52	0.862	1.38
366	1.5 × 10 ⁻³	0.272	1.70	0.203	0.612	
	2.0 × 10 ⁻³	0.284	1.94	0.216	0.804	
	2.5 × 10 ⁻³	0.296	2.01	0.246	0.826	
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ C ₂ O ₄] ⁺	313	3.0 × 10 ⁻³	0.362	1.68	0.227	0.232
		4.0 × 10 ⁻³	0.369	1.76	0.229	0.284
		5.0 × 10 ⁻³	0.379	1.79	0.234	0.274
	254	0.75 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.572	2.86	0.814	0.572
		1.00 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.602	3.02	0.869	0.612
		1.25 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.625	3.14	0.903	0.640

penta-ammine complex gives higher redox yield than tetra-ammine complex, while the photoaquation yield is higher with tetra-ammine, $\phi_{total} = (\phi_{redox} + \phi_{aquation})$, being the same (Table 3). This may be correlated with the spectral feature of the two complexes. For the tetra-ammine complex, 366 nm band lies in the L₂ ligand field band and this is separated from the CTTM band through a minimum at 310 nm while for penta-ammine the L₂ band superimposes with the CTTM band, thus the 366 nm transition is more of CTTM character in case of penta-ammine compared to tetra-ammine complex. The variation of $\phi_{redox}/\phi_{aquation}$ with wavelength can not be explained by the radical-pair model.

The photoredox quantum yield increases in anaerobic condition (Table 2). Similar increase was observed earlier⁴. Formation of H₂O₂ in aerobic photolysis and dependence of $\phi_{Co^{2+}}$ on initial concentration of the complex in anaerobic photolysis (Table 2) suggest that the photoreleased C₂O₄^{•-} radical in aerobic medium is preferentially scavenged by oxygen producing H₂O₂, while in anaerobic medium C₂O₄^{•-} radical reduces a ground state Co(III) complex molecule, thus increasing the quantum yield of Co²⁺ in absence of oxygen. Direct participation of oxygen was further supported by the fact that photolysis in aerobic medium (where the solution was not saturated with oxygen)

TABLE 3—QUANTUM YIELDS OF DIFFERENT PRODUCTS FROM Co(III)-TETRA-AMMINE *Bis*-OXALATO AND Co(III)-PENTA-AMMINE OXALATO COMPLEX

Complex	Irradiation wavelength nm (Concentration moles/liter)	Medium	ϕ_{AA}^a	ϕ_{OA}^b	ϕ_{Total}	$\frac{\phi_{Redox}}{\phi_{Total}}$	$\frac{\phi_{AA}}{\phi_{Total}}$	$\frac{\phi_{OA}}{\phi_{Total}}$	$\frac{\phi_{Redox}}{\phi_{Aquation}}$
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ HC ₂ O ₄] ⁺	366 (2.0 × 10 ⁻³)	Aerobic	0.427	0.175	0.860	0.30	0.50	0.20	0.43
		Anaerobic	1.080	0.168	1.720	0.27	0.63	0.10	0.38
	313 (5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	Aerobic	0.055	0.035	0.235	0.62	0.23	0.15	1.61
		Anaerobic	0.076	0.050	0.326	0.614	0.23	0.15	1.59
	254 (1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	Aerobic	1.580	0.250	2.220	0.18	0.71	0.11	0.22
		Anaerobic	1.340	0.465	2.405	0.25	0.56	0.19	0.33
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ C ₂ O ₄] ⁺	366 (2.0 × 10 ⁻³)	Aerobic	0.606	0.103	0.885	0.20	0.685	0.116	0.25
		Anaerobic	0.804	0.074	1.160	0.245	0.693	0.063	0.32
	313 (2.0 × 10 ⁻³)	Aerobic	0.138	0.053	0.469	0.594	0.294	0.113	1.46
		Anaerobic	0.274	0.044	0.697	0.544	0.393	0.063	1.19
	254 (1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	Aerobic	0.96	0.258	1.61	0.245	0.595	0.160	0.32
		Anaerobic	0.61	0.568	1.78	0.338	0.343	0.319	0.51

AA^a—Ammonia aquated products for penta and tetra-ammino complexes.

OA^b—Oxalato aquated products for penta and tetra-ammino complexes.

(pH = 3.72, Temp. 35°).

